

DATABRI-X: Data Process & Technological Bricks for expanding digital value creation in European Data Spaces

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Abstract

The emergent European Data Economy relies on the availability of data as a basis for further innovation and exponential development of technologies, especially the development of trustworthy ‘made in Europe’ AI that reflects European values. Data Spaces, platforms and marketplaces are enablers, key to unleash the potential of such data. However, data sharing and data interoperability are still at their infancy. Through DataBri-X, European Data Spaces, platforms and marketplaces will be equipped with a holistic and flexible data governance process and a seamless integrated standards-based toolbox.

The project's objective is to provide a holistic, energy-efficient and user-friendly toolbox of practical, robust and scalable bricks/Bri-X (processes, technologies and tools) that improve the interoperability, usability, discoverability, quality, and integrity of data and metadata, with the aim of making data sets ready for expanded digital value creation in the context of European Data Spaces.

Keywords 1

Data Governance, Data Spaces, Data curation, Semantic Interoperability

1. Project information

- Project short name/acronym: DataBri-X
- Project full name: Data Process & Technological Bricks for expanding digital value creation in European Data Spaces
- Project website link: [Home - DataBri-X Project](#)
- Start date: 01/10/2022
- End date: 30/09/2025
- Project status: Ending project
- Funding agency: European Commission
- Funding programme: Horizon Europe
- Call identifier: HORIZON-CL4-2021-DATA-01-03
- Project partners:
 - a. ATHINA-EREVNITIKO KENTRO KAINOTOMIAS STIS TECHNOLOGIES TIS PLIROFORIAS, TON EPIKOINONION KAI TIS GNOSIS
 - b. EBOS TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED
 - c. NOVA TELECOMMUNICATIONS SINGLE MEMBER SA
 - d. TECHNISCHE INFORMATIONSBIbliothEK (TIB)
 - e. SEMANTIC WEB COMPANY GMBH
 - f. LSTECH ESPANA SL
 - g. FUNDACION IMDEA NETWORKS
 - h. GUARDTIME OU

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- i. DEUTSCHES FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM FUR KUNSTLICHE INTELLIGENZ GMBH
 - j. WOLTERS KLUWER DEUTSCHLAND GMBH
 - k. INTERNATIONAL DATA SPACES EV
 - l. SIEMENS AKTIENGESELLSCHAFT OESTERREICH
 - m. OXFORD SEMANTIC TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED
- Project logo: [Promotional Materials - DataBri-X Project](#)
 - Project video [DataBri-X project - YouTube](#)

2. Project summary

Through DataBri-X, European Data Spaces, platforms and marketplaces and their wide range of business, governmental and public, research and civil society stakeholders will be equipped with a holistic and flexible data governance process and a seamless integrated standards based toolbox for data- and metadata management which can be assembled along relevant requirements, provides open source as well as commercial tools, and mechanisms to load 3rd party resources like language resources or AI models, and can be easily deployed into Data Spaces.

DataBri-X specified, developed and now demonstrates a data management toolbox, that is based on a data governance process called JenPlane that can be configured in a flexible way via the DataBri-X Knowledge Graph (DataBri-X KG) along the requirements of a data management project. DataBri-X therefore follows the JenPlane Data Governance approach. This approach describes the data lifecycle like a plane instead of a cycle, which introduces a highly iterative and flexible lifecycle model. JenPlane is enabling users to select the most appropriate, energy-efficient and complementary combination of tools for their data management activities. The JenPlane Process Designer & Composer answer the challenge of tool selection, collaboration & orchestration and cater for the need of, semi-automatic deployment, execution, and orchestration of data intensive projects. As such, the JenPlane approach provides the assurance of a consistent and coherent execution plan for the tools most suited for the data management activities of a variety of end-users, thus securing the usability and end-user friendliness of the toolbox.

The DataBri-X toolbox brings together more than 25 existing data management tools and frameworks which were expanded where necessary to support the full DataBri-X Data Governance (Data Life Cycle), e.g., to enable dynamic augmented metadata capability. As of the overall target of data sharing and management of DataBri-X in the field of European Data Spaces and beyond, DataBri-X has a strong focus on interoperability. In addition, DataBri-X provides a DataBri-X Resource Connector that allows to load and use resources from 3rd party systems like the ELG (language resources, trained models, vocabularies), and is based on the IDS Data Space Connector approach, following the IDS Information Model.

Both the governance layer as well as the DataBri-X toolbox are tested in three real-world use cases from different domains:

- First a telecommunication use case that improves the company internal data-intensive flows in order to support social media brand equity or service performance in a call center environment.
- Second an energy use case that enables a faster and more comprehensive creation and testing of energy communities.
- Third a legal use case that collects the business requirements of a European legal Data Space and provides first workflows to analyse and enrich legal data in several languages.

3. Project available results

The project's results so far can be categorized in two main areas:

- Project Deliverables, which indicate the approach taken, the work executed and the collaboration that happened within the consortium. The deliverables can be found here: [Public Deliverables - DataBri-X Project](#)
- Project webinars (13 one hour webinars so far) that showcase the general objectives, the governance layer, the tools and the toolbox as well as the three industry use cases: [DataBri-X project - YouTube](#)

4. Relevance to ESWC conference

Data Spaces, Semantic Operability and Knowledge Graphs are all over the place. DataBri-X addresses at least one core aspect of this challenge in a systematic fashion: Data Governance. Only with proper Data Governance in place, Data Spaces can work and can be commercially successful.

DataBri-X is in its final stage, so a lot of work has been done and can be reported, explained and used by other projects that are just about to start. So they could get an easy kick start with things that are necessary, but probably not at the core of their project resources. By making sure that exploitation of DataBri-X results is successful, project networking is a win-win for both sides. In addition, the personal exchange will extend existing networks for future collaboration on these same topics, since Data Governance is needed everywhere.

5. Value brought by the project to ESWC participants

The project deals with a hot topic in the Semantic Web community. It is focused on Data Governance and its impact on semantic interoperability.

DataBri-X could share knowledge about methodologies, knowledge implementation, Data Space connectors and Data Governance ontology implementation. And since it is the end of the project, a lot of discussion could be around lessons learned, so what to do and what not to do, which is often extremely helpful from a practical point of view.

6. Value gained by the project from ESWC participation

Our main goal is to support our exploitation activities. So creating awareness of our project results, which could lead to further uptake in new projects, new collaboration in new calls and an extension of our networks. In addition, we could compare our solutions with the results in similar projects – so a real lesson learned for the future beyond the limitations of our own approach.

Acknowledgments

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